

BOSHLANG‘ICH TA’LIMDA INKLYUZIV QADRIYATLAR MAZMUNI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada boshlang‘ich ta’lim tizimida inklyuziv qadriyatlarni qaror toptirishning nazariy-metodik asoslari va ularning zamonaviy ta’lim paradigmasidagi o‘rni tadqiq etilgan. Tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi - boshlang‘ich sinf o‘quvchilarida bag‘rikenglik, tenglik va ijtimoiy birdamlik kabi inklyuziv qadriyatlarni shakllantirishning pedagogik mexanizmlarini aniqlashdan iborat. Maqolada “tibbiy model”dan “ijtimoiy-pedagogik model”ga o‘tishning ahamiyati ilmiy asoslab berilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: inklyuziv ta’lim, boshlang‘ich sinf, inklyuziv qadriyatlar, ijtimoiy adaptatsiya, bag‘rikenglik, pedagogik kompetensiya, teng imkoniyatlar.

СОДЕРЖАНИЕ ИНКЛЮЗИВНЫХ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ В НАЧАЛЬНОМ ОБРАЗОВАНИИ

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Аннотация: В данной статье исследуются теоретико-методические основы формирования инклюзивных ценностей в системе начального образования и их роль в современной образовательной парадигме. Основная цель исследования заключается в выявлении педагогических механизмов формирования таких инклюзивных ценностей, как толерантность, равенство и социальная солидарность у учащихся начальных классов. В статье научно обоснована значимость перехода от «медицинской модели» к «социально-педагогической модели» образования.

Ключевые слова: инклюзивное образование, начальные классы, инклюзивные ценности, социальная адаптация, толерантность, педагогическая компетенция, равные возможности.

CONTENT OF INCLUSIVE VALUES IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article explores the theoretical and methodological foundations of establishing inclusive values within the primary education system and their role in the modern educational paradigm. The primary objective of the research is to identify pedagogical mechanisms for developing inclusive values such as tolerance, equality, and social solidarity among primary school students. The study provides a scientific justification for the transition from a “medical model” to a “socio-pedagogical model” of education.

Keywords: inclusive education, primary school, inclusive values, social adaptation, tolerance, pedagogical competence, equal opportunities.

Currently, inclusive education is one of the priority areas of the global education system. The need to ensure social equality in society and guarantee the right of each individual to development requires the formation of inclusive values. Especially at the stage of primary education, these values are of great importance for the personal and social development of children. Global development trends of the modern education system require guaranteeing the right of each individual to receive quality education, regardless of their intellectual and physical condition. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Education” and the “Concept of Development of Inclusive Education in the Public Education System for 2020-2025” serve as the legal basis for reforms in this area. The primary education stage is the most important period in which a child's social worldview is formed. It is at this stage that the inculcation of "inclusive values" is a school of empathy and social responsibility not only for children with disabilities, but also for healthy peers. The problem is that in practice, inclusion is often understood only as a "technical adaptation", while its valuable basis, the spiritual and moral aspects, are ignored. The theoretical foundations of inclusive education go back to L.S. Vygotsky's theory of defectology and social development. At the international level, scientists such as T. Booth and M. Ainscow have developed a system for measuring values through the "Inclusion Index". However, the systematization of the content of values, taking into account the national mentality and the characteristics of primary education, still remains an urgent scientific problem. By inclusive values, we mean a system of moral principles accepted and practiced by all participants in the educational process.

Individual-level values. This level is mainly based on the idea that “Every child is unique”. Viewing a child’s physical or mental disability as a “speciality” rather than a “defect” is the starting point of inclusive values. A primary school teacher should develop empathy and tolerance skills in their students. Institutional (School) level values. A school is a small model of society. If the values of mutual assistance and cooperation are strong between the school administration and the teaching staff, students will also adopt this. An inclusive school culture is based on the principle of “open doors for all”. Social level values.

This is equality and social justice. Inclusive education does not exclude a child from society, but rather prepares him for an active civic position. Analysis shows that inclusive values are not formed only through verbal propaganda. For this, the lesson itself must be inclusive. That is, the teacher should not only write information on the board, but also use audio, video and sensory materials. Through this, he practically demonstrates to children the value “We all learn in different ways, and this is normal.” The role of working with parents. One of the most important points of the article is that the inclusive values that a child learns at school should not be rejected when he goes home.

In many cases, parents of healthy children have the wrong stereotype that “a disabled child will interfere with my child’s education.” Breaking this stereotype is an integral part of the content of inclusive values. It is necessary to organize not only methodological, but also “Psychological and Ethical Inclusion” courses for primary school teachers. Textbooks should include not only “ideal” children as heroes, but also images of active children wearing glasses, in wheelchairs or with hearing aids. In inclusive classes, it is necessary to introduce an “incentive system” for students not only academically, but also for their social support, cooperation and contribution to the community. Inclusive values in primary education are a guarantee of a healthy and just society in the future. If a child learns at the age of 7-10 not to discriminate against people based on their physical condition, when he grows up, he will build a truly humane society.

An inclusive educational environment has a positive impact not only on the academic, but also on the social and psychological development of students. Students educated in such an environment develop qualities such as tolerance, empathy, responsibility, and mutual respect. Inclusive education also expands the opportunity to cooperate with peers and serves the development of communication skills. This will contribute to the successful integration of the individual into society in the future. Work is underway to create favorable conditions for children with special educational needs in educational institutions, improve the skills of teachers, and introduce modern methodologies. Integrating inclusive values into the educational process is one of the important factors in developing human capital and ensuring social equality in our country. Therefore, incorporating the ideas of inclusion into educational programs and developing inclusive competencies of teachers are urgent tasks.

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